

Borderline Personality Disorder in Adolescents: Diagnostic Reluctance & Dearth of Literature!

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ABSTRACT

In child & adolescent mental health settings, borderline personality disorder (BPD) is a dominant and substantial condition with high occurrence rates seen in community, crisis, and in-patient settings. Previously because of multiple concerns, BPD diagnosis in adolescents was considered questionable and was perceived to be invalid. However, in light of the evidence, recent guidelines and diagnostic manuals affirm the diagnosis in the under-18 population. However, despite this, the subsequent lack of clinical literature focusing on this topic highlights diagnostic reluctance among clinicians and thus underscores the need to communicate this new knowledge about BPD in adolescence to healthcare professionals.

Keywords: Adults; Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD); Diagnosis; Borderline Personality Disorder; BPD; DSM V; DSM 5; Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders 5; DSM-5; Adolescents

Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) is a type of personality disorder. A personality disorder is usually conceptualised as a behavioural manifestation of rigid and unhealthy thinking patterns^[1]. BPD significantly impacts a person's ability to manage and regulate their emotions. This can lead to marked affective instability, low frustration tolerance, increased impulsivity, difficulty controlling anger, recurrent self-harming & suicidal behaviours & threats, and negatively affects not only how a person thinks about themselves but also has a detrimental impact on their relationships with others^[2]. We already knew that BPD is one of the most common types of personality disorders diagnosed in adults^[3], and it was widely accepted that like other personality disorders, it has its roots in infancy, childhood, and adolescence^[4]. Subsequently, it was realised that not only does it have its roots in the childhood and adolescent period, but it could also be fully formed as a disorder and thus could be diagnosed in the under-18 population. Previously, however, detecting BPD before eighteen years of age had been arguable^[5] because of the following fears. Firstly, it was thought that the validity of the diagnosis in adolescents was questionable as some of the common characteristics of BPD (affective instability and disturbance in self-identity) could be seen as common features in adolescents. Secondly, there were concerns about the lack of any diagnostic

manual backing the issuance of this diagnosis in under-18s. Thirdly, because of the negative connotations attached to the diagnostic term(s), some clinicians would be reluctant to give the diagnosis. However, subsequent research showed that there is a lot of evidence available in support of both detecting and treating BPD in the under-18 population. It is found to be effective and consistent in youth as it is in adulthood^[6,7] and similar consistency is observed in youth as in adulthood^[8]. Most importantly, disorder-specific therapy, especially early intervention, is effective^[9]. Thus, national treatment guidelines (NICE), DSM-5, and the proposed International Classification of Diseases, 11th Revision, personality disorder classification have all recently confirmed the legitimacy of the BPD diagnosis in adolescents^[10-12] and have provided relevant diagnostic criteria, too. Since BPD is associated with receiving clinical attention and causes psychosocial impairments, it is more widely studied than other personality disorders^[13]. The aforementioned developments, in terms of guidelines and research evidence, make one think that there might have been a shift in the clinicians' attitude towards diagnosing BPD and managing it in adolescents. But is this really the case? Or are we still stuck in avoiding acknowledging its presence in patients who are under-18? To answer this, a systematically informed literature review^[14] tried to look at the evidence. As we know, the new diagnostic manuals have affirmed the diagnosis of BPD in youngsters, the aim of this systemically informed review was to explore whether clinicians and researchers are using the available manual to diagnose BPD in adolescents and to see whether there are any studies published on this topic using the DSM-5 criteria. The hypothesis was that not many clinicians or researchers are aware of or using the opportunity to diagnose and thus manage BPD in adolescents, i.e., early in the course of this illness. This would also in turn highlight, if there are not many studies, that there is an urgent necessity to transfer this new information about BPD in youngsters to healthcare professionals as we know from evidence that early diagnosis and treatment are the keys to minimise impact and debilitation from any lifelong disorder such as BPD. However, the results confirmed that there is a dearth of clinical literature looking at or commenting on the diagnosis of BPD in adolescents- only 2 studies looked at the topic under discussion. This is surprising because, in young mental health settings, BPD is a dominant and substantial condition, with a probable occurrence of 11% in psychiatric casualties and up to 50% in inpatient settings^[15,16]. Furthermore, because of the severity and chronic nature of BPD, these patients use clinical resources more extensively than patients with other personality disorders or other mental illnesses like major depression^[17]. There is also a significant impact, from untreated BPD, on the life of service users biologically, psychologically, and socially^[18] and so, it would be expected that clinicians would be less reluctant to diagnose it now given the support of the relevant guidelines and the diagnostic modules. In conclusion, despite the research and diagnostic allowance, there still seems to be reluctance among clinicians to diagnose BPD in adolescents. It could safely be advised to consider the possibility of BPD in adolescents who display features suggestive of it and to apply the relevant criteria to patients to facilitate early detection and treatment to prevent long-term consequences. This should be a part of the routine practice of clinicians dealing with service users who are under-18. Although there might be an appropriate concern in case of lack of specialist services to manage this disorder, however, there still would be value in correctly identifying and diagnosing the disorder as, at the very least, it will allow the patients to understand their condition better and permit some role for psycho-education and insight development.

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